

ON THE ESTIMATION OF FUMARIC AND MALEIC ACIDS.

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It has been shown that fumaric and maleic acids can be estimated in acid solution, in presence of succinic acid and phosphates with mercuric sulphate as catalyser.

In connection with a work in this laboratory it was necessary to estimate small amounts of fumaric acid in presence of succinic acid and phosphate buffers. Estimation by KMnO_4 , either in acid or in alkaline solution as proposed by Straub (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1935, 1, 236) and Strumm (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1937, 47, 791), were not suitable because (i) KMnO_4 oxidises fumaric as well as succinic acid and (ii) the reaction between KMnO_4 and fumaric acid is not stoichiometric, but increases with the added amount of KMnO_4 with no definite end-point. The three second end-point suggested by Straub was found not to give good results.

McMargasches and Hinner (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1924, 64, 61) suggested the possibility of estimating fumaric acid by bromination in nearly neutral solutions. This method was studied extensively by Szegedy (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1937, 109, 95). He has shown that the p_H value of the solution must be controlled at p_H 8.4, otherwise erratic values would be obtained. Moreover at a p_H value above the transition point of phenolphthalein, the bromination of succinic acid is not nil. The direct halogenometric estimation of fumaric acid in presence of phosphates at p_H 9.4 gives high values (Szegedy, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1937, 109, 316). Hence Szegedy recommends that when phosphates are present in the solution, fumaric acid should be previously separated as mercurifumarate. The objection to the estimation of fumaric acid in acid solution seems to be due to the slowness of the reaction. In this connection Frieman, Kennedy and Lucas (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 722) have shown that the direct estimation of acetylenes can be carried out by direct bromination in presence of HgSO_4 as catalyst. This method has been developed by Lucas and Pressmann (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1935, 10, 149) and a comprehensive scheme has been drawn up for the estimation of various unsaturated compounds by the bromate-bromide mixture, amongst which have been included maleic and fumaric acids. But no experiment was carried out by them in presence of succinic acid and phosphates. In view of the long time required for the complete bromination of maleic and fumaric acids in acid solution, even in presence of HgSO_4 (30-35 mins.), the elucidation of the effect of these two substances was thought desirable.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The method of titration was similar to that described by Lucas and Pressman (*loc. cit.*).

A known excess of bromate-bromide mixture (10 to 15%) was taken in the titration vessel and the flask was evacuated. 5 c.c. of 6N-H₂SO₄ were added and allowed to stand for 2-3 minutes, while the bromine was being liberated. The flask was then wrapped with a black cloth and the respective quantities of 0.2N-HgSO₄ and the solution to be analysed were run in without breaking the vacuum. The wash-liquid in no case exceeded 10% of the total volume. The flask was then shaken well and allowed to stand in the dark for 30 to 35 minutes. 2N-NaCl solution (15 c.c.) was then added to liberate the bromine and then 5 to 10 c.c. of 20% KI. The flask was shaken for $\frac{1}{2}$ minute, the vacuum broken, and the liberated iodine was then titrated by N/50-Hypo solutions. All the reactions were carried out at room temperature.

Titration of Fumaric Acid alone.

TABLE I.

Effect of change of HgSO₄.

1.15 C.c. N/10-KBrO₃ + 5 c.c. 6N-H₂SO₄ + 0.2N-HgSO₄ + 10 c.c. fumaric acid solution containing 0.00584N-acid allowed to stand for 40 minutes ; 5 c.c. of 2N-NaCl added. Back titrated with KI and hypo.

0.2N-HgSO ₄	KBrO ₃ consumed.		0.2N-HgSO ₄ .	KBrO ₃ consumed.	
	Actual.	Theoretical.		Actual	Theoretical.
5 c.c.	0.992 c.c.	1.00 c.c.	10 c.c.	0.980 c.c.	1.00 c.c.
8	1.02	"	15	1.00	"

TABLE II.

Effect of variation of time.

1.15 C.c. N/10-KBrO₃ + 5 c.c. 6N-H₂SO₄ + 5 c.c. 0.2N-HgSO₄ + 10 c.c. of fumaric acid.

Time.	KBrO ₃ consumed.		Time.	KBrO ₃ consumed.	
	Actual.	Theoretical.		Actual	Theoretical.
10 min.	0.750 c.c.	1.00 c.c.	30 min.	1.04 c.c.	1.00 c.c.
20	0.975	"	40	0.992	"

TABLE III.

Titration of fumaric acid in presence of phosphates.

1.15 C.c. $N/10$ - $KBrO_3$ + 5 c.c. $6N-H_2SO_4$ + 0.2 N - $HgSO_4$ + 5 c.c. of $M/15-Na_2HPO_4$ + 10 c.c. of fumaric acid. Reaction allowed to continue for 30 mins.

$HgSO_4$.	$KBrO_3$ consumed.		$HgSO_4$.	$KBrO_3$ consumed.	
	Actual.	Theoretical.		Actual.	Theoretical.
7.5 c.c.	0.900 c.c.	1.00 c.c.	15.0 c.c.	0.995 c.c.	1.00 c.c.
10.0	0.950	"	20.0	1.01	"
			25.0	0.987	"

Effect of Succinic Acid on the Estimation of Fumaric Acid in presence and absence of Phosphates.

TABLE IV.

Effect of bromate mixture on succinic acid alone.

3.0 C.c. $N/10$ - $KBrO_3$ + 10 c.c. $HgSO_4$ + 5 c.c. $6N-H_2SO_4$ + 10 c.c. 0.05 N succinic acid.

Time.	$KBrO_3$ consumed (from back titration by Hypo).	Time.	$KBrO_3$ consumed (From back titration by Hypo).
* 10 mins.	Nil	40 mins.	Nil.
20	"	35	0.01 c.c.
		40	Nil

TABLE V.

Estimation of fumaric acid solution containing succinic acid and phosphates.

1.15 C.c. $N/10$ - $KBrO_3$ + 5 c.c. $6N-H_2SO_4$ + 15 c.c. 0.2 N - $HgSO_4$. The reaction allowed to continue for 30 mins.

$N/20$ -Succinic acid.	$N/300$ -Fumaric acid.	$M/15-NH_2HPO_4$.	$N/10$ - $KBrO_3$ consumed. Obs.	Theor.
5 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	...	0.985 c.c.	1.00 c.c.
10.0		...	1.02	"
15.0		...	1.03	"
5.0		5.0 c.c.	0.980	"
20.0	*5.0	"	0.505	0.50
20.0	*3.0	"	0.295	0.30
20.0	*1.0	"	0.110	0.10

* In cases marked with asterisk, $KBrO_3$ solution added was from 0.55 c.c. to 0.125 c.c.

Estimation of Maleic Acid in presence of Succinic Acid and Phosphates.

TABLE VI.

Conditions exactly the same as in the estimation of fumaric acid.

N/10-Succinic acid.	N/100-Maleic acid.	M/15-Na ₂ HPO ₄ .	KBrO ₃ consumed.	
			Obs.	Theor.
10.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	1.02 c.c.	1.00 c.c.
10.0	15.0	5.0	1.485	1.50
10.0	20.0	5.0	1.980	2.00
10.0	25.0	5.0	2.50	2.50

Comparison of Szegedy's Method and the Mercuric Sulphate Method in Estimating Fumaric Acid from a Solution containing M/15- phosphate.

TABLE VII.

Fumaric acid actually taken.	Obs. value by Szegedy's method after separation as mercurifumarate.	Obs. value by mercuric sulphate method.
0.00584 g.	0.00582 g.	0.00580 g.
0.1168	0.1145	0.1170
0.01752	0.01750	0.01748

It will be observed that whereas at p_H 8.4, high values were obtained by Szegedy in the direct halogenometric titration of fumaric acid in presence of phosphates, low values were obtained when fumaric acid was titrated alone in acid solution in presence of phosphates. It seems probable that whereas HPO₄' and H₂PO₄' are capable of catalysing the bromination of fumaric acid, undissociated H₃PO₄ probably retards the bromination.

Further work is in progress in this direction.

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